

WAYS OF TEACHING DIALOGIC SPEECH IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS

Ra'noxon Maxsudaliyeva

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Izoh: Ushbu maqolada chet tili darslarida interaktiv metodlardan foydalangan holda dialogik nutqni o'rgatish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar va uning sinfda o'qitish usullari keltirilgan. Maqolada monologik metodni zamonaviy o'qitish ehtiyojlari va pedagogika hamda boshqa fanlar yutuqlariga muvofiq qayta tasdiqlashga yo'naltirilgan tadqiqot natijalarining bir qismi tahlil qilinadi. Fanlararo tadqiqotning asosiy e'tibori yangi o'qitish usullarini ochish emas; ko'proq zamonaviy o'qitishda dialogik metodni samarali qo'llash imkonini beruvchi topilmalar va standartlarni nazarda tutgan holda mavjud o'qitish uslubining yangi didaktik asosini taklif qilishdir.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены исследования по обучению диалогической речи на уроках иностранного языка с использованием интерактивных методов и способы ее преподавания на уроке. В статье анализируется часть результатов исследования, направленного на подтверждение монологического метода в соответствии с современными педагогическими потребностями и достижениями педагогики и других наук. Акцент междисциплинарных исследований делается не на выявлении новых методов обучения; скорее, это предложить новое дидактическое обоснование существующего метода обучения, обращаясь к поиску стандартов, позволяющих эффективно применять диалогический метод в современном обучении.

Annotation: This article presents research on teaching dialogic speech in foreign language lessons using interactive methods and its ways of teaching in the classroom. The paper analyzes a part of the results of a research oriented to reaffirmation of monologic method in accordance to contemporary teaching needs and achievements of pedagogy as well as other sciences. The emphasis of the interdisciplinary research is not to reveal new teaching methods; it is rather to offer a new didactic grounding of the existing teaching method, referring to finding and the standards enabling efficient implementation of dialogic method in contemporary teaching.

Kalit so'zlar: dialogik nutq, chet tilini o'rgatish, interaktiv metodlar, kommunikativ funksiya.

Ключевые слова: диалогическая речь, обучение иностранному языку, интерактивные методы, коммуникативная функция.

Key words: dialogic speech, teaching foreign language, interactive methods, communicative function.

The main and leading goal in the teaching of foreign languages in primary school is a communicative goal, which determines the entire educational process. One of the main forms of speech communication is Dialogic speech. The development of Dialogic speech in the studied foreign language is one of the most acute problems of modern pedagogical science. This is confirmed by a number of studies, articles, manuals that have appeared recently. Nevertheless, this issue requires further methodological permits, as the modern requirements to the dialogical speech is to teach students to converse in the target foreign language is not always fully implemented. This situation requires a new search for a more rational method of teaching Dialogic speech, in which the desired practical results would be achieved in the shortest way, with minimal time and effort, and the learning process would be feasible, interesting and fun for students.¹

Despite the fact that Dialogic speech is more complicated than monologue, and from the point of view of the tension of attention, and in terms of diversity and quality of speech patterns used, and for a number of other reasons, however, in terms of consistency in the teaching of oral speech, preference should be given to Dialogic speech. After all, it is through dialogue that individual speech patterns, entire structures, which are then used in monologue speech, are practiced and remembered. Already at the initial stage of learning English, students can, and the teacher should help them to acquire the ability to use the target language for communication. At the initial stage, the oral beginning from the first steps creates conditions for the disclosure of the communicative function of the language, taking into account the ability of the student 8-10 years to easier perception of speech and reproduction of heard and brings the learning process closer to the conditions of real communication, which causes students' interest in the subject and speaking about the tasks of teaching dialogue.²

It should be noted that the method of teaching Dialogic speech not so long ago stood out in an independent aspect of teaching oral speech. In this area, there are still many issues that require theoretical and experimental research. Among them are: the ratio of dialogical and monologue speech in the high school course; principles and techniques of creating a communicative environment in the classroom; the characteristics of perception of speech in the dialogue process; the selection of the situations underlying the learning dialogue at different

¹ Borozova E. V. Dialogic speech as the purpose and means of teaching English. - University of Russia, Moscow: Russia, 2019, - 122p.

² Vygotskiy L.S. The Importance of Dialogue in Teaching and Learning. -Oxford University Press, 2016, - 199p.

stages of learning; methods of creating a dialogic speech situation in the classroom; the possibility of using for teaching dialogue; selection of material for teaching dialogue.

Dialogue is a form of speech in which statements are exchanged directly between two or more persons. Dialogic speech has its own characteristics in relation to the selection, design and functional orientation of the use of language material. Thus, it is characterized by the use of introductory words, interjections, stamps, expressions of evaluative nature, reflecting the reaction of the speaker to the information received, denying or confirming the expressed idea, expressing doubt, surprise, desire, etc.³

Dialogue is characterized by the widespread use of extralinguistic means of expression of thought: gestures, facial expressions, indications of surrounding objects. The correlation in the speech of non-language characters is defined as pragmatism. The situation - a set of circumstances, conditions that create a particular relationship, situation or situation - facilitates communication, helps to save language resources in teaching pupils. Dialogic speech solved the following main tasks: first, to give the concept of dialogue in all its diversity, in its natural form, so that the children are convinced that the question-answer form - only a private, although the most common case of dialogic communication. In various examples, to show students that it will only be lively, natural and truly Dialogic, if the data replicas will include greetings, announcements, invitations, expression of different kind of feelings (of surprise, gratitude, certainty, doubt), evaluation of facts, etc. secondly, to teach children the necessary remarks, to train them to the level of automaticity when used in a particular situation. Thirdly, to teach students to exchange these remarks in appropriate situations, i.e. to teach them to conduct a dialogue. The implementation of these tasks, in addition to purely methodological techniques, helps directly language material textbooks with a system of lexical collections, special exercises and texts as experience has shown, one of the effective means of creating a motive for foreign language communication of students are non-traditional methods of learning. These include role-playing and dramatization.

In methodical literature role-playing game is defined as spontaneous behavior of students, their reaction to the behavior of other people involved in a hypothetical situation. Role-playing game is a kind of educational technique in which the student must speak freely within the given circumstances, acting as one of the participants in foreign language communication. A mandatory

³ Borozova E. V. Dialogic speech as the purpose and means of teaching English. - University of Russia, Moscow: Russia, 2019, - 124p.

element of the game is to resolve the problem situation. Role-playing game, based on the solution of a problem, provides maximum activation of communicative activity of students. The search for a solution to this problem determines the naturalness of communication.⁴

The formulation of the problem and the need to solve it also serve to develop critical thinking among students. And finally, the need for careful consideration of the situation, finding the right solution develops logical thinking, the ability to argue and counter-argue, convince the interlocutor. The teacher and students conditionally include four stages (for example, the dramatization of the fairy tale "the Turnip"). 1. Familiarization with the situation. The teacher sets the scenery (cardboard house), which is then always associated with the children of the theater. The teacher invites students to prepare a production of the fairy tale "Turnip" and announces that the theater needs actors for the roles of grandfather, grandmother, granddaughter, etc. Having formed the troupe, the teacher introduces the necessary vocabulary. In this case, it's the word turnip, the phrase Here I am. Instead of words, grandparents are invited to use the well-known children Mummy, Daddy. Problem statement. The teacher explains that before playing a role, each student should find out everything about turnip with the help of available language means, trying to use as many familiar words and structures in the dialogue as possible.

2. Dramatization. Here is an example. Daddy (walking across the stage, stops suddenly): Oh, what is this? Is this a flower? (Answers himself.) Is is a small tree? Oh, it's a turnip! It is Masha's turnip! What a big yellow turnip! (He tries to pull a turnip out of the ground.) One, two, three.... Mummy, come here! M u m m y: Oh, what's this? Is this a flower or turnip? Daddy: This isn't a flower. It's a turnip! Mummy: Who turnip is this? Daddy: it's Masha's turnip. (Trying to pull a turnip.) One, two, three, four Mummy: Masha, come here! Masha: Oh, what's this? Is it my turnip? Mummy and Daddy (together): Yes, it is! (Pull the turnip.) One, two, three, four, five.... Then the action continues in the same way. The dramatization ends with the phrase "turnips": Here I am! ⁵

In conclusion, the teacher thanks the actors, asks the jury to name the best student (the one who used more vocabulary, while making fewer mistakes) and, if necessary, analyzes the speech of the actors in terms of grammar, vocabulary, usage, etc. in the form of recommendations to the next performances. The more

⁴ Budnichenko E. P. Teaching Dialogic speech in English lessons. Foreign languages at school. - Belgrade University Press, 2012, - 204-205p.

⁵ Ariyan M. A. the Use of educational potential of speech etiquette in a foreign language. - Multidimensional Research Journal, 2022, - 67-68p.

often the teacher refers to the theatrical performances in the classroom, the less time and effort spent on familiarization with the situation and formulation of the problem and the more often students can change roles. This is very important for the development of speech skills in different situations. The use of theater in the classroom shows the high efficiency of this technique, primarily for the development of skills and abilities of unprepared oral speech based on the motivation of speech actions.

Thus, non-traditional methods of teaching Dialogic speech give a strong motive to learn the language, they help to create a language environment close to natural. There is an opportunity to activate on this basis almost all the program lexical and grammatical material of the initial and subsequent stages of training.⁶ Students quickly master speech structures and formulas (in certain situations), then automatically operate them when performing communicative tasks of another kind. Students much faster to acquire a sense of language. Such classes provide an additional opportunity for the development of listening skills: children perceive the speech of students of other classes, allow students to get acquainted with the literature of the country of the studied language; contribute to the aesthetic education of students, familiarizing them with the culture of the country of the studied language.

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⁶ Mirzayunusova Z. Methods of Teaching Dialogic Speech to Students in Uzbek Schools. - Central Asian journal of social sciences and history, 2022, - 98p.